

Impact of Individual Dimension of Knowledge-sharing on Collaborative Research Publications among Academic Librarians in University Libraries, North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: This study investigates the impact of individual dimensions of knowledge-sharing on collaborative research publications among academic librarians in Northeast Nigeria. Knowledge-sharing is crucial for fostering research collaboration and enhancing intellectual growth.

Method: A survey research design was adopted, with data collected through structured questionnaires administered to 112 academic librarians from selected universities in the region. Total enumeration sampling was used, and 106 valid responses were analysed. Descriptive statistics addressed the research objectives, while a hypothesis was tested using simple regression analysis in SPSS (Version 27).

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that knowledge-sharing significantly contributes to personal intellectual growth and confidence among academic librarians. A positive relationship was established between knowledge-sharing and the volume of collaborative research publications. However, certain individual dimensions, such as reciprocity and personal reputation, had a lesser influence.

Implications: These findings highlight the need for institutional policies that promote open knowledge exchange and skill development to enhance research productivity.

Conclusion: The study concludes that knowledge-sharing positively influences collaborative research, though some individual dimensions play a minimal role.

Recommendations

To strengthen research output, the study recommends targeted professional development programmes to improve librarians' communication competencies, institutional policies that encourage knowledge-sharing culture, adoption of mentorship initiatives and digital collaboration tools to enhance research networks and inter-institutional collaboration

Keywords: Knowledge-sharing, Collaborative Research, Publication, Individual Dimension, Academic Librarians

Introduction

Collaborative research is a partnership between two or more parties who work together to achieve common goals. “Collaborative (or participatory) research is seen as “researchers coming together to produce new scientific knowledge. It is research, involving coordination between researchers, institutions and academic librarians. *It can furthermore*, be seen as that act which involves a mutual conspiracy of two or more participants to solve a scientific problem together, irrespective of individual differences. There are numerous terms that are interchangeable with “research collaboration.” Co-authorship, research partnership, research networking, joint research, participatory research, and other similar terms (Ubogu & Chukwusa, 2023). In collaborative research, parties are more closely aligned in the sense of “working together” to reach the desired outcome, rather than that outcome being achieved through “individualistic” participation. (Dyson, Howley & Shen, 2021). Expounding to this, Singh, Sharma, and Paliwal (2021), posited that, “collaboration enhances effectiveness and efficiency in research.

It is important to note that, research publications play a crucial role in the career advancement of academic librarians, with studies consistently showing a strong correlation between publication output and professional growth (Crampsie, 2020). Khan, Ibrahim, and Hussain (2021) also confirmed that a librarian's publication record is the primary factor influencing their career progression. Collaborative research publications (CRPs) among academic librarians have gained significant importance as the profession

continues to evolve in response to the changing needs of academia (Colon, & Bright, 2024).

Collaborative research publications (CRPs) entail academic librarians actively participating in research endeavors and contributing as co-authors or collaborators in generating scholarly publications. It refers to academic or scholarly works that result from collaborative efforts among researchers, scholars, or academics from multiple institutions or disciplines. In CRPs, two or more individuals contribute their expertise, resources, and findings to produce a joint publication, such as journal articles, conference papers, book chapters, reports, or other scholarly outputs. Furthermore, it involve multiple researchers working together to conduct a study and publish their findings. These collaborations can be within the same institution, across different organizations, or even internationally. The goal is to combine expertise, resources, and perspectives to enhance the quality and impact of the research (Adelowo, Ilevbare, & Orewole, 2022).

As research practices become very complex and the demands for interdisciplinary expertise increase, librarians engage in collaborative research to contribute to scholarly discourse and enhance their professional development (Näverå, & Olsson, 2022). Collaborative efforts among librarians enhance their knowledge in data management, scholarly communication, and digital resources, fostering innovation and supporting the research community through best practices and insights (Olanusi, 2023).

Moreso, CRPs is anchored on the concept of knowledge-sharing, which has become increasingly important in the realm of collaborative research, particularly within academic and professional settings (Kim, et al., 2024). Expounding on this, Bell and Kennan, (2021), posited that collaborative research publications (CRPs), have become an important strategy in the field of academic librarianship, enhancing the profession's impact, fostering scholarly contributions, and creating a dynamic network for knowledge-sharing within the library community.

Various factors trigger collaborative research publications, including knowledge-sharing (Adelowo, Ilevbare, & Orewole, 2022). This involves the exchange of information and skills among individuals, teams, or organizations. And it involves distributing valuable information to enhance learning, foster innovation, and improve performance. Knowledge-sharing can take place through formal training, informal conversations and collaborative projects. Kucharska and Erickson (2023), describes it as the transfer of both explicit and implicit experiences, along with concepts and skills that encourage innovation at work.

Knowledge-sharing is the process of exchanging information, skills, expertise or insights among individuals, teams or organization to help improve learning, innovation and decision-making. Essentially, individuals contribute what they have learned and transfer their knowledge to others who share a common interest and find the information valuable. This process involves gathering, structuring, and communicating knowledge from one person to another (Budiyono, & Tunas, 2024). The main elements of knowledge-sharing involve its purpose, which is to deepen both individual and collective understanding, enhance decision-making and problem-solving abilities, and promote innovation and creativity. Furthermore, knowledge-sharing can be categorized into two types: tacit knowledge, which refers to personal, experience-based knowledge that is challenging to articulate or document (such as insights, intuition, and skills), and explicit knowledge, which consists of information that is easily expressed, documented, and shared (such as manuals, reports, and procedures).

There are dimensions of knowledge-sharing (Gómez-Pérez, 2019). In a broader perspective, knowledge-sharing is one of the most important and complex activities among all knowledge management processes and requires managers (academic librarians), to focus on the following three key areas (dimensions): individual, organizational, and technological (Edward 2011). The complexity of knowledge-sharing occurs because these three dimensions can be difficult to manage and can influence the knowledge-sharing process. The individual dimension of knowledge-sharing, is the main focus in this study, generally refers to, the personal factors that influence how individual share knowledge within a library (Cabrera, Collins, & Salgado, 2006). These individual dimensions encompass various aspects which includes:

Knowledge-sharing is influenced by cognitive, behavioral, emotional, and social dimensions. The **cognitive dimension** involves knowledge awareness, expertise, and cognitive ability, all of which determine an individual's capacity and willingness to share knowledge (Sackett et al., 2024). The behavioral dimension focuses on personal motivation, communication skills, and active knowledge contribution, which drive the sharing process (Meenambigai & Lokeshwaran, 2017). The emotional dimension highlights trust and reciprocity, ensuring shared knowledge is used responsibly and exchanged mutually. The social dimension emphasizes interpersonal relationships, social norms, and collaboration, which foster engagement and knowledge exchange. Studies suggest that individual factors, alongside organizational and IT-related aspects, significantly impact knowledge-sharing behaviour (Ammar, Hayder, & Norashikin, 2014). Moreover, quantitative research underscores the role of personal attributes in shaping knowledge-sharing practices (Chedid, Alvelos, & Teixeira, 2022).

Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the extent of individual dimension of knowledge-sharing in fostering collaborative research among academic librarians in universities libraries, North-East, Nigeria.
2. Determine the frequency of collaborative research publications among academic librarians in university libraries, North-East, Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

HO1 There is no significant relationship between of individual dimension of knowledge-sharing and collaborative research publications among academic librarians, in university libraries, North-East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In today's knowledge-driven academic environment, collaborative research publications among academic librarians, are essential for advancing scholarship, improving library services, and fostering professional development. Knowledge-sharing plays a critical role in collaboration, as it enables librarians to exchange ideas, skills, and experiences that contribute to high-quality research outputs. However, despite the recognized importance of knowledge-sharing, the extent to which individual dimensions - such as tacit and explicit knowledge-sharing, motivation, trust, communication, and technological support, effect collaborative research publications remain unclear.

Many academic librarians, encounter challenges in sharing knowledge effectively due to factors such as lack of institutional support, inadequate technology infrastructure, concerns about intellectual property and individual reluctance to collaborate. While previous studies have explored knowledge-sharing in general, there is limited research on how specific dimensions of knowledge-sharing (individual Dimension), influence collaboration research publications among academic librarians and understanding the typical make-up of this individual dimension of knowledge-sharing, is crucial to understanding how it enhances collaborative research productivity among academic librarians.

Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the impact of individual dimension of knowledge-sharing on collaborative research publications, among academic librarians in North-East, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Knowledge-sharing plays a crucial role in academic environments, particularly in enhancing collaborative research efforts. Among academic librarians, knowledge-sharing fosters innovation, improves service delivery, and facilitates high-impact scholarly publications. This study's review, examines the individual dimension of knowledge-sharing - which includes and not limited to motivation, trust, expertise, personal attitudes; etc and their influence on collaborative research publication.

Motivation, trust, expertise, and personal attitude play crucial roles in shaping knowledge-sharing behavior among academic librarians. Motivation, as explained by self-determination theory, influences librarians' willingness to share knowledge, with intrinsic factors like intellectual curiosity and extrinsic incentives such as institutional rewards driving engagement (Hagger & Hamilton, 2020; Goh & Sandhu, 2013). Trust and reciprocity are fundamental enablers of knowledge-sharing, as librarians are more likely to exchange knowledge when they believe in the credibility and reliability of their colleagues (Sen, 2024; Fullwood et al., 2013). Trust fosters open communication and collaboration, while reciprocity—the expectation of mutual benefits—further encourages participation in knowledge exchange (Li, Zhang, & Chen, 2024). Additionally, expertise and experience significantly impact knowledge-sharing behaviours, with experienced librarians often mentoring junior colleagues to promote a collaborative research culture (Rochmaningsih, Sridadi, & Augustina, 2025). However, fear of losing a competitive advantage may lead to knowledge hoarding (Lin, 2007). Personal attitude and willingness determine librarians' engagement in collaborative research, as those with a positive, communal mindset are more likely to share knowledge, whereas individualistic perspectives may hinder participation (Bock et al., 2005). A collaborative attitude enhances teamwork, boosts research productivity, and contributes to institutional knowledge development (Hislop, 2003).

Collaborative research publications among academic librarians have become a growing trend in academia, as they promote interdisciplinary knowledge exchange and increase research impact (Aryani, 2024). Among academic librarians, collaboration leads to improved research quality, increased citation rates, and a more diverse knowledge base. Factors such as institutional support, access to digital tools and collaborative platforms (e.g., Google Scholar, ResearchGate, and Institutional Repositories), further facilitate joint research efforts (Owan, Asuquo, Etudor-Eyo, & Makuku, 2021).

Despite the benefits, several barriers hinder knowledge-sharing and collaborative research among academic librarians. These challenges include: lack of institutional support, time constraints, technological barriers and knowledge hoarding among others.

Methodology

This study used a survey research design, which is appropriate for gathering insights from a sample population to represent a larger academic community and analyze their perceptions regarding knowledge-sharing and collaborative research publications. The target population consists of 112 academic librarians from selected university libraries in Northeast Nigeria. A total enumeration sampling technique was adopted, ensuring that all identified librarians were included in the study. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was designed to capture demographic information (age, gender, years of experience, institution type), individual dimensions of knowledge-sharing, and the frequency of collaborative research publications among academic librarians.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to measure respondents' perceptions. To ensure validity and reliability, the instrument was subjected to expert review and a pilot study was conducted to refine the questions for clarity and consistency. Data collection was carried out through direct administration and electronic distribution to maximize response rates. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and frequency) to summarize responses, while inferential statistics, specifically linear regression analysis, was conducted using SPSS software to test the null hypothesis and determine the impact of individual dimensions of knowledge-sharing on collaborative research publications among academic librarians. This methodological approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between knowledge-sharing practices and research collaboration within university libraries.

Result and Discussion

Extent of Individual Dimension of Knowledge-sharing on Collaborative Research Publications

S/No.	Items	SA	A	N	D	SD	X	Std.
1	I share my knowledge with others when I am confident about my ability to perform knowledge-sharing.	53 (49.5)	27 (25.2)	12 (11.2)	9 (8.4)	6 (5.6)	4.05	1.208

2	I would rather share my knowledge with those, who would share their knowledge and experience in return.	19 (17.8)	37 (34.6)	17 (15.9)	17 (15.9)	17 (15.9)	3.22	1.348
3	I share my knowledge and experience with colleagues because I want to benefit from others.	30 (28.0)	31 (29.0)	16 (15.0)	17 (15.9)	13 (12.1)	3.45	1.368
4	My inability to share knowledge and collaborate with others in research, is a result of inadequate communication and interpersonal skills.	33 (30.8)	42 (39.3)	21 (19.6)	1 (0.9)	10 (9.3)	3.81	1.167
5	My intellectual horizon increases when I indulge in collaborative knowledge-sharing.	42 (39.3)	40 (37.4)	11 (10.3)	5 (4.7)	9 (8.4)	3.94	1.204
6	I share my knowledge and experience with colleagues because I want to gain a personal reputation.	30 (28.0)	16 (15.0)	19 (17.8)	13 (12.1)	29 (27.1)	3.05	1.580
7	Sometimes, I do not feel motivated enough to share my knowledge with my colleagues.	37 (34.6)	31 (29.0)	10 (9.3)	13 (12.1)	16 (15.0)	3.56	1.448
Aggregate mean							3.58	0.893

The study reveals a moderately strong tendency towards knowledge-sharing practices among academic librarians in universities in northeast Nigeria. The majority of respondents share knowledge when confident in their abilities, with a mean score of 4.05. However, sharing knowledge with individuals who reciprocate by sharing their own experiences received mixed responses. The majority view knowledge-sharing as mutually beneficial, with 28.0% strongly agreeing and 29.0% agreeing. Inadequate communication and interpersonal skills are considered to hinder collaboration, with a mean of 3.81. Engaging in collaborative knowledge-sharing broadens intellectual horizons, with 39.3% strongly agreeing and 37.4% agreeing. Sharing knowledge for personal reputation is less strongly endorsed, with a lower mean score of 3.05. Motivation is a factor, but not a significant barrier for most respondents. The findings suggest that, while knowledge-sharing is strongly favoured when it leads to personal intellectual growth and confidence, the importance of reciprocity and personal reputation is less pronounced, and communication skills are seen as critical for effective collaboration.

Frequency of Collaborative Research Publications

Frequency of Collaborative Research Publications	Frequency	Percent (%)
Never	9	8.4
Rarely	24	22.4
Sometimes	31	29
Often	20	18.7
Always	23	21.5
Total	107	100

This table shows that 8.4% of respondents have never participated in collaborative research publications, and 22.4% rarely participate. Meanwhile, 29% indicated they sometimes participate in such publications, and 18.7% reported they often participate. Only 21.5% stated they always participate in collaborative research publications. Based on these responses, it can be concluded that most respondents have some level of participation in collaborative research publications, making them well-positioned to provide information on knowledge-sharing in these contexts among academic librarians in university libraries in North-East Nigeria.

There is no significant relationship between of individual dimension of knowledge-sharing and collaborative research publications among academic librarians, in university libraries, North-East, Nigeria.

Linear regression table on the Impact of Individual Dimension of Knowledge-sharing (KS) Use on the Frequency of Collaborative Research Publications

Individual Dimension of Knowledge-sharing on Collaborative Research Publications	R	R ²	F	β	Df	Sig.
	.919 ^a	.844	566.786	.970	106	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Frequency of Collaborative Research Publications (CRP)

b. Predictors: (Constant) Extent of Use of Knowledge-sharing (KS)

The regression analysis investigates the impact of the extent of knowledge-sharing (KS) use on the frequency of collaborative research publications. The correlation coefficient (R = 0.919) indicates a very strong positive relationship between these two variables. This suggests that as knowledge-sharing increases, the frequency of collaborative research

publications also rises significantly. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.844$) reveals that 84.4% of the variance in collaborative research publications is explained by the extent of knowledge-sharing use. This high R^2 value suggests that knowledge-sharing is a strong predictor of research collaboration, leaving only 15.6% of the variation to be explained by other factors not included in the model.

The F-statistic ($F = 566.786$) is notably high, indicating that the regression model as a whole is highly significant. This strong F-value confirms that the relationship between knowledge-sharing and collaborative research publications is not due to chance but is statistically meaningful. The beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.970$) further emphasizes the impact of knowledge-sharing on research collaboration. A beta value close to 1.0 means that for every unit increase in knowledge-sharing use, the frequency of collaborative research publications increases by 0.970 units. This implies that improving knowledge-sharing mechanisms can substantially enhance research collaborations. With 106 degrees of freedom ($Df = 106$), the study appears to be based on a robust sample size, which strengthens the reliability of the findings. Additionally, the significance level ($Sig. = 0.000$) confirms that the relationship between knowledge-sharing and research collaboration is highly statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This means there is strong evidence to conclude that knowledge-sharing plays a crucial role in enhancing collaborative research efforts.

Discussion

The study reveals a moderately strong inclination towards knowledge-sharing among academic librarians in universities in northeast Nigeria. Respondents predominantly share knowledge when confident in their abilities (mean = 4.05), while reciprocity in knowledge-sharing received mixed responses. A majority (28.0% strongly agreeing, 29.0% agreeing) view knowledge-sharing as mutually beneficial, though inadequate communication skills (mean = 3.81) are seen as a barrier to collaboration. Intellectual growth is a key motivator, with 39.3% strongly agreeing and 37.4% agreeing that knowledge-sharing broadens perspectives. However, sharing for personal reputation is less significant (mean = 3.05), and motivation is not a major barrier.

The regression analysis highlights a strong positive correlation ($R = 0.919$) between knowledge-sharing and collaborative research publications, with knowledge-sharing explaining 84.4% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.844$). The high F-statistic ($F = 566.786$) confirms the model's significance, and the beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.970$) indicates that increased

knowledge-sharing significantly enhances research collaboration. With 106 degrees of freedom and a highly significant p-value (Sig. = 0.000), the findings strongly support the crucial role of knowledge-sharing in fostering research collaboration. Improving communication skills and fostering a culture of knowledge exchange can further enhance collaborative efforts among academic librarians.

Conclusion

The study highlights the critical role of knowledge-sharing in promoting collaborative research among academic librarians and more so, the impact of individual dimension of knowledge-sharing in publication output of academic librarians. Efforts to increase motivation, improve communication skills, and provide platforms for virtual collaboration could further enhance knowledge-sharing practices and collaborative research outcomes. This study contributes to the understanding of knowledge-sharing among academic librarians in academic libraries and offers valuable insights for enhancing research collaboration in the northeast region.

Recommendations

The study recommends the following:

1. Increase training and workshops to enhance librarians' knowledge of adequate maximization of knowledge-sharing and its benefits for collaborative research publication and linking knowledge-sharing performance, to career progression and promotions.
2. Promotion of culture where academic librarians share knowledge, with or without the expectation of mutual benefit; hence, strengthening research collaboration and publication and to improve communication and interpersonal skills among academic librarians to facilitate better collaboration.

References

Näverå, E., & Olsson, A. K. (2022) Library-faculty Collaboration in the Light of a Business Administration Bachelor's Program: 'The Scientific Wave.' *Nordic Journal of Information Literacy in Higher Education* 13(1) 39-55, <https://doi.org/10.15845/noril.v13i1.3781>

- Adelowo, C. M., Ilevbare, O. E., & Orewole, M., Oladotun. (2022) Collaboration, Networking and Research Productivity in Nigeria's Research Institutes: Empirical Evidence. *International Journal of Business Reflections* 3(2) 153-171, <https://doi.org/10.56249/ijbr.03.01.32>
- Ammar D. N, Hayder S. H, Norashikin A., (2014) Factors Influencing Knowledge-Sharing in Organizations: A Literature Review, *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 3(9),1314-1319, doi: <https://www.doi.org/10.21275/SEP14397>
- Aryani, A. (2024). Research Collaboration Network. *Front Matter* <https://doi.org/10.59350/y6xqx-0ef43>
- Bell, E. C., & Kennan, M. A. (2021) Partnering in Knowledge Production: Roles for Librarians in the Digital Humanities. *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association* 70 (2)157-176, <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750158.2021.1907886>
- Budiyono, H., H., & Tunas, B. (2024) Knowledge Sharing Behavior Shaped by Organizational Climate, Social Network, Perception, and Achievement Motivation. *International Journal of Research and Review* 11(2)161-171, <https://doi.org/10.52403/ijrr.20240218>
- Bock, Zmud, Kim, & Lee. (2005) Behavioral Intention Formation in Knowledge Sharing: Examining the Roles of Extrinsic Motivators, Social-Psychological Forces, and Organizational Climate. *MIS Quarterly* 29(1) 87, <https://doi.org/10.2307/25148669>
- Cabrera, Á., Collins, W. C., & Salgado, J. F. (2006) Determinants of Individual Engagement in Knowledge-sharing. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management* 17(2) 45-264, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190500404614>
- Chedid, M., Alvelos, H. and Teixeira, L. (2022) Individual factors affecting attitude toward knowledge sharing: an empirical study on a higher education institution", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, 52 (1) 1-17, <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-01-2020-0015>
- Colon Aguirre, M., & Bright, K. (2024) What do Liaison Librarians Do? An Exploration into the Tasks and Perceptions of the Role. *Proceedings of the ALISE Annual Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.21900/j.alise.2024.1678>

- Crampsie, C., Neville, T., & Henry, D. (2020) Academic Librarian Publishing Productivity: An Analysis of Skills and Behaviors Leading to Success. *College & Research Libraries* 81(2) <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.2.248>
- Fan, Z., & Beh, L.-S. (2024) Individual motivation and knowledge sharing: the hindering effect of perceived costs in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education* 50(2) 419-437, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2024.2341112>
- Fullwood, R., Rowley, J., & Delbridge, R. (2013) Knowledge sharing amongst academics in UK universities. *Journal of Knowledge Management* 17 (1) 123-136, <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673271311300831>
- Gómez-Pérez, A. (2019) Knowledge Sharing and Reuse. *The Handbook of Applied Expert Systems* 10(1)10-36, <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780138736654-10>
- Granquist, S., & Lindsay, V. (2024) Scholar One - Examining the Relationship Between Knowledge-sharing, Individual Trust, and Multinational Team Performance in a Virtual Setting: A Non-Experimental Study. *SAGE Publications* <https://doi.org/10.31124/advance.171215080.03226659/v1>
- Hagger, M. S., & Hamilton, K. (2020) General causality orientations in self-determination theory: Meta-analysis and test of a process model. *European Journal of Personality* 35(5) 710-735, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0890207020962330>
- Hislop, D. (2003) Linking Human Resource Management and Knowledge Management via Commitment. *In journal of Employee Relations* 25 (2) 182-202, <https://doi.org/10.1108/01425450310456479>
- Kim, J., Park, S., Castruita-Rios, Y., Weathers, M., Park, M., Inge, K., Riesen, T., Keeton, B., Avellone, L., & Tansey, T. (2024) Customized employment for transition-age youth in state vocational rehabilitation program PY2017 - PY2020: Analysis of service outcomes and related factors. *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation* 60(3) 281-297 <https://doi.org/10.3233/jvr-240013>
- Li, Y., Wu, Y., Zhang, L., & Chen, J. (2024) The Impact of Network Structure on Knowledge Adoption: A Network Text Analysis on Knowledge-Sharing Platforms. *IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems* 11 (1)1467-1482 <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcss.2023.3255588>

- Mohammad, M. T. F., Alajmi, S. A., & Ahmed, E. A. R. D. (2018) Motivation Factors Toward Knowledge Sharing Intentions and Attitudes. *International Journal of Business Administration* 9(4) 110 <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijba.v9n4p110>
- Nasirova, G., Soatova, G., Tilovova, G., & Makhim, A. (2023) A Review of Individual Level Knowledge Sharing in the Workplace. *International Journal of Innovation and Economic Development* 9(4) 22-28 doi <https://doi.org/10.18775/ijied.1849-7551-7020.2015.94.2003>
- Owan, V. J., Uzoamaka Duruamaku-Dim, J., Nonyelum Odigwe, F., & Owan, M. V. (2022) Dataset of the Adoption of Digital Tools for Research sharing among Academics in African Varsities during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. *F1000Research* 11(82) <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.54245.2>
- Rochmaningsih, A., Sridadi, A. R., & Agustina, T. S. (2025) Systematic Literature Review: Importance of Knowledge Sharing on Organization (Antecedents & Consequences). *Accounting and Management Journal* 8(2)109-118 <https://doi.org/10.33086/amj.v8i2.6764>
- Sackett, P. R., Demeke, S., Bazian, I. M., Griebie, A. M., Priest, R., & Kuncel, N. R. (2024) A Contemporary look at the Relationship between General Cognitive Ability and Job Performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 109 (5) 687-713, <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001159>
- Sen, A. (2024) Organizational Knowledge and Knowledge Management - A New Framework. *American Journal of Management Science and Engineering* 9 (1) 1-12, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajmse.20240901.11>